

Effect of bariatric procedure types on Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis in morbidly obese patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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Abstract

Purpose: Determine effect of bariatric procedure types on Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis in morbidly obese patients

Method: The initial search was based on relevant keywords in the electronic databases PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, EBSCO and Embase between 2011 to September 2021. The mean difference and effect size was calculated with 95% confidence interval (CI) by fixed effect model and inverse variance method. Meta-analysis was performed using Stata / MP v.16 software.

Result: Overall Mean differences of BMI between after and before bariatric surgery in Morbid Obese patients was -12.19 (MD, 95% CI -12.73, -11.65). Overall effect size of improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after surgery in Morbid Obese patients was 55% (MD, 95% CI 51%, 60). Based on findings, significantly improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after bariatric surgery observed.

Conclusion: bariatric surgery can significantly improve the histological and biochemical manifestations of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. Roux-en-Y gastric bypass was more effective than other surgical procedures.

Key words: Morbid Obese Patients, bariatric surgery, steatosis, steatohepatitis, fibrosis

Introduction

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is the most common chronic liver disease caused by the accumulation of fat in the liver(1). Obesity is very common in adolescents and adults and is associated with a significant increase in the incidence of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease(2). Evidence suggests that by 2030, the prevalence of NAFLD in the adult population

will increase to 33.5%, and as a result, the incidence of liver-related deaths should be increased(3). NAFLD is a common liver disease with changes such as steatosis, steatohepatitis and cirrhosis(4). Studies have shown that more than a third of people with NASH may develop fibrosis after 5 to 10 years(5, 6). Studies have also reported that about 90% of patients undergoing bariatric surgery have NAFLD (7-10). Evidence suggests that the progression of fibrosis decreases or stops with weight loss due to surgery(11, 12). However, there is insufficient evidence on the effect of various bariatric surgeries on NAFLD and few studies have been performed in this field. In the present study, we tried to report a comprehensive result regarding the effect of various bariatric surgery methods on Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis and steatosis in obese people. Therefore, the present study was performed to investigate the effect of bariatric procedure types on Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis in morbidly obese patients.

Method

The initial search was based on relevant keywords in the electronic databases PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, EBSCO and Embase between 2011 to September 2021. All studies were selected according to inclusion criteria. The present study was a systematic review and meta-analysis based on the key considerations of the PRISMA statement(13).

Searches were performed with mesh terms:

("Bariatric Surgery"[Mesh]) OR ("Bariatric Surgery/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Bariatric Surgery/classification"[Mesh] OR "Bariatric Surgery/complications"[Mesh])) OR "Gastric Bypass"[Mesh]) OR ("Gastric Bypass/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Gastric Bypass/classification"[Mesh] OR "Gastric Bypass/complications"[Mesh])) OR "Cholecystectomy, Laparoscopic"[Mesh]) OR "Gastroplasty"[Mesh]) OR ("Gastroplasty/adverse effects"[Mesh] OR "Gastroplasty/classification"[Mesh] OR "Gastroplasty/economics"[Mesh])) AND "Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease"[Mesh]) OR ("Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease/classification"[Mesh] OR "Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease/complications"[Mesh] OR "Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease/diagnosis"[Mesh] OR "Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease/statistics and numerical data"[Mesh] OR "Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease/surgery"[Mesh] OR "Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease/therapy"[Mesh])) AND ("Biopsy"[Mesh] OR "pathology" [Subheading])) AND "Obesity"[Mesh].

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Body mass index between 35 and 40, any type of bariatric surgery, randomized clinical trial studies, Randomized controlled trials studies, controlled clinical trials; Prospective and retrospective cohort studies, observational study, in human and weight loss on liver histology. case control studies, in vitro studies, animal studies, case reports and reviews were excluded from the study.

Data Extraction and analysis method

Author's name, year of publication, age, sex, number of biopsies body mass index (BMI), weight loss, Duration between biopsy, type of Intraoperative biopsy were reported. Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) (14) used to assessed quality of the cohort studies and case-control studies,

This scale measures three dimensions (selection, comparability of cohorts and outcome) with a total of 9 items. In the analysis, any studies with NOS scores of 1-3, 4-6 and 7-9 were defined as low, medium and high quality, respectively. The quality of randomized studies included was assessed using Collaboration's tool(15). The scale scores for low risk was 1 and for High and unclear risk was 0. Scale scores range from 0 to 6. A higher score means higher quality.

Two blind browsers extracted the data independently from the full text of the selected studies, and the third browser then examined the data. Prior to screening, kappa statistics were performed to confirm the level of agreement between the reviewers. Kappa values was 0.80 estimated that this value is appropriate and high.

The mean differences and effect size was calculated with 95% confidence interval (CI) by fixed effect model and inverse variance method. Random effects were also examined to address potential heterogeneity, with a coefficient of I^2 indicating heterogeneity, a coefficient above 50% indicating moderate to high heterogeneity. Meta-analysis was performed using Stata / MP v.16 software.

Result

First, the search was performed using primary keywords and 145 studies were found in the database. After removing 32 duplicate studies, the abstract of 113 studies was reviewed. At this stage, 88 studies that did not meet the inclusion criteria were excluded from the study and the full text of 25 studies was reviewed independently by two blind authors. Then 17 studies were deleted at this stage and only eight studies were selected to enter the meta-analysis (Figure1).

Figure 1. PRISMA flowcharts

Characteristics

Seven prospective studies and one retrospective study have been included in present article. The number of patients a total were 1207 (male: 240; female: 967) with mean age of 40.26±9.7 years. Mean of Weight lose were 66.77±22.9 kg (Table1).

Table1. Demographic information of Morbid Obese patients

Study. Years	Study design	Number of patients		Mean of age	Mean of Pre.B MI (kg/m ²)	Mean of Post.B MI (kg/m ²)	Mean of weight loss (kg)	Number of biopsy pairs
		male	female					
Algooneh et al., 2016 (16)	prospective	28	56	42	46.6	33.3	55.7	84
Cazzo et al., 2015 (17)	prospective	13	50	40.1	37.4	26	90	63
Taitano et al., 2015 (18)	prospective	26	134	47	52	33	62	160
Caiazzo et al., 2014 (19)	prospective	108	431	40	46.8	40	33.7	317
Moretto et al., 2012 (20)	retrospective	19	59	40	45.4	29.3	83	78
Vargas et al., 2012 (21)	prospective	7	19	45	49	30	72	26
Tai et al., 2012 (22)	prospective	8	13	30	43.8	28.3	71	21
Karcz et al., 2011 (23)	prospective	31	205	38	45	29.5	NR	223

Assessing risk of bias

According to NOS tool, all studies have a moderate to high risk of bias and Overall quality of studies were low.

Body mass index

Overall Mean differences of BMI between after and before bariatric surgery in Morbid Obese patients was -12.19 (MD, 95% CI -12.73, -11.65) with high heterogeneity ($I^2 = 98.17\%$; $P = 0.00$) (Figure2). Based on findings, BMI decreased significantly after bariatric surgery.

Subgroup Meta-analyses:

Mean differences of BMI between after and before sleeve gastrectomy in Morbid Obese patients was -14.92 (MD, 95% CI -15.98, -13.87) with low heterogeneity ($I^2 = 41.20\%$; $P = 0.19$) among two studies (Figure2).

Mean differences of BMI between after and before Roux-en-Y gastric Bypass in Morbid Obese patients was -18.93 (MD, 95% CI -20.18, -17.69) with high heterogeneity ($I^2 = 87.97\%$; $P = 0.00$) among four studies (Figure2).

Mean differences of BMI between after and before laparoscopic adjustable gastric banding in Morbid Obese patients was -6.90 (MD, 95% CI -7.69, -6.11) among one study (Figure2).

Mean differences of BMI between after and before mixed surgery in Morbid Obese patients was -19 (MD, 95% CI -20.98, -17.02) among one study (Figure2).

Improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease

Overall effect size of improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after surgery in Morbid Obese patients was 55% (MD, 95% CI 51%, 60) with moderate heterogeneity ($I^2 = 63.23\%$; $P = 0.01$) (Figure3). Based on findings, BMI significantly improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after bariatric surgery.

Subgroup Meta-analyses:

Mean differences of improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after sleeve gastrectomy in Morbid Obese patients was 53% (MD, 95% CI 46, 61) with low heterogeneity ($I^2 = 0.0\%$; $P = 0.52$) among two studies (Figure3).

Mean differences of improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after Roux-en-Y gastric Bypass in Morbid Obese patients was 52% (MD, 95% CI 47%, 58%) with low heterogeneity ($I^2 = 9.37\%$; $P = 0.35$) among four studies (Figure3).

Mean differences of improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after laparoscopic adjustable gastric banding in Morbid Obese patients was 86% (MD, 95% CI 64%, 1.08%) among one study (Figure3).

Mean differences of improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after mixed surgery in Morbid Obese patients was 75% (MD, 95% CI 59%, 91%) among one study (Figure3).

Figure2. Forest plot showed BMI between after and before surgery in Morbid Obese patients

Based on the findings of selected studies, and because few studies have looked at steatosis, steatohepatitis, or fibrosis, the data were not able to be meta-analyzed and were systematically reviewed.

Studies have shown that the improvement in steatosis was about 90% in patients who underwent wedge biopsy, and about 86% in patients who underwent needle core biopsy; as can be seen in the wedge biopsy group, the improvement in steatosis was higher than in the needle core biopsy group.

Studies have shown that the cure for steatohepatitis was about 83% in patients who underwent wedge biopsy, and about 47% in patients who underwent needle core biopsy; as can be seen in the wedge biopsy group the improvement in steatohepatitis was higher than in the needle core biopsy group.

Studies have shown that the improvement in fibrosis was about 47% in patients who underwent wedge biopsy, and about 26% in patients who underwent needle core biopsy; as can be seen in

the wedge biopsy group, the improvement in fibrosis was higher than in the needle core biopsy group.

Figure3. Forest plot showed improves nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after bariatric surgery

Discussion

In the present study, 1207 patients were studied. The mean age of patients was 40 years. Based on the findings, steatosis and steatohepatitis in most patients after bariatric surgery had a significant improvement. According to the findings of studies, bariatric surgery can improve liver fibrosis by up to 30%. Examination of bariatric surgery and subgroup meta-analysis showed that about 55% of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease was cured and Roux-en-Y gastric bypass had a greater effect on the histological features of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease than other method. Evidence suggests that bariatric surgery is associated with improved biochemical

properties of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. It is practically impossible to evaluate fibrosis after surgery because longitudinal data have not been reported in this field and the studies selected were not suitable for the study of fibrosis and focused only on steatosis and steatohepatitis. Based on the findings of a meta-analysis conducted by Mummadi et al., 2008 in a population of 766, improvement in non-alcoholic fatty liver disease was observed after bariatric surgery (24). Chavez-Tapia et al., 2010 (25) reported improvement in steatosis scores after bariatric surgery. In a Systematic Review of Liver Biochemistry and Histology, Bariatric surgery is associated with a significant reduction in the weighted incidence of a number of histological features of NAFLD including steatosis (50.2 and 95 %CI of 35.5–65.0), fibrosis (11.9 and 95 %CI of 7.4–16.3 %), hepatocyte ballooning (67.7 and 95 %CI 56.9–78.5) and lobular inflammation (50.7 and 95 %CI 26.6–74.8 %). Surgery is also associated with a reduction in liver enzyme levels, with statistically significant reductions in ALT (11.36 u/l, 95 %CI 8.36–14.39), AST (3.91 u/l, 95 %CI 2.23–5.59), ALP (10.55 u/l, 95 %CI 4.40–16.70) and gamma-GT (18.39 u/l, 95 %CI 12.62–24.16). Heterogeneity in results was high (26). As can be seen in the findings section, there is a high heterogeneity between studies, this heterogeneity affects the overall results and future studies should be done more carefully. The limitations of the present study include the lack of reporting on the duration of follow-up of patients, the type of biopsy performed, the reasons for patient selection, histological interpretation, and most importantly, the high heterogeneity between studies.; The risk of study bias was also high.

Conclusion

Based on the result, meta-analysis showed that the mean BMI change after bariatric surgery is 12.19, and bariatric surgery can significantly improve the histological and biochemical manifestations of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. Roux-en-Y gastric bypass was more effective than other surgical procedures. Due to the high heterogeneity between studies, further studies should be performed to confirm the evidence; finally, it is recommended that bariatric surgery be performed in obese patients to potentially reduce the histological and biochemical manifestations of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.

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